

Table 2. Plant characteristics of VL Dhan 221 and Bala.

Character	VL Dhan 221	Bala (check)	Character	VL Dhan 221	Bala (check)
Plant height (cm)	90–95	65–70	Alkali digestion score ^b	2–3	2–3
Days to 50% flowering ^a	67–91	65–102	Gelatinization temperature ^b	Intermediate	Intermediate
Flag leaf	Erect	Erect	Amylose content ^b	Mid-High	Mid-High
Panicle type	Compact	Compact	Protein content ^b (%)	9.42	9.37
Panicle axis	Droopy	Droopy	Mineral ^b (%)	1.27	1.59
Awn type	Awnless	Awnless	Disease and insect pest reaction ^c		
Grain color	Straw	Straw	Leaf blast	4	5
1,000-grain wt (g)	22.7	17.2	Neck blast	3	7
Hulling percentage	71.4	71.8	Sheath rot	5	7
Grain length (mm)	8.23	6.47	Leaf scald	4	7
Grain width (mm)	2.81	2.88	Pink stem borer	5	5
Brown rice length (mm)	5.85	4.68	<i>Sesamia inferens</i>		
Brown rice width (mm)	2.49	2.40	Leafroller <i>Cnaphalocrocis</i> medinalis	5	7
Length:width	2.35	1.95			
Brown rice shape	Medium	Bold			
Volume expansion ^b	3.40	2.87			

^aRange at different locations over several years. ^bBased on brown rice. ^cMaximum score recorded using *Standard evaluation system for rice* (0–9) during 1985–87.

grow in 2 yr with a 150% cropping intensity. Regional farmers may be able to adopt a more economical rice-based cropping system (rice - wheat/barley/lentil/pea) with a 200% cropping intensity under rainfed conditions by cultivating VL Dhan 221, which is suitable for sowing in June. □

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Integrated germplasm improvement—deepwater

NDGR150 and NDGR151: two promising lines for semi-deepwater areas of eastern Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

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Deepwater rice is grown on about 390,000 ha in eastern UP. About 2/3 of this area is under semi-deepwater conditions (50–100 cm) during the cropping period. Madhukar, Chakia 59, and local traditional varieties are currently cultivated in these areas. Suitable substitutes for these cultivars must be semitall and have good elongation ability, nonlodging plant type, photoperiod sensitivity, and high yield potential.

NDGR 150 and NDGR151 are sister lines from IET4060/Jalmagna. They are 135–175 cm (depending upon water depth) and have moderate tillering, kneeing, and elongation ability. They flower in late October, are photoperiod sensitive, and have well-exserted, compact panicles. Distinguishing traits include panicle lengths from 27 to 29 cm and 1,000-grain weights of 27.0–30.2 g. NDGR150 has white kernels; NDGR151, red kernels.

Table 1. Yield performance of promising lines and checks in station and in farmers' field trials. Ghagharaghat, UP, 1988–90.

Entry	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	Station				32 farmers' fields			
	1988	1989	1990	Av	1988	1989	1990	Av
NDGR150	2.5	3.5	2.2	2.7	1.7	1.8	2.2	1.9
NDGR151	2.6	3.7	2.9	3.0	1.9	2.0	2.3	2.1
Sabita (national check)	1.7	2.9	2.1	2.1	1.5	1.4	2.1	1.6
Madhukar (local check)	1.4	2.2	1.1	1.5	1.6	0.9	1.5	1.3
Maximum water depth (cm)	65	52	45				45–95	

Table 2. Performance of promising lines and checks in regional and national trials in UP, 1987–90.^a

Site and year ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	NDGR150	NDGR151	Madhukar ^b	Sabita ^c	Tilakkachari ^c
<i>Adaptive trials</i>					
Bahraich					
1989 (56)	2.1	2.0	1.1	1.7	
1989 (51)	2.8	3.7	1.5	2.3	
Ballia					
1988 (45)	3.1	4.0	2.3	3.4	
1989 (75)	1.9	2.5	1.8	1.7	
Kuraumi					
1988 (60)	3.2	3.4	2.3	3.0	
1989 (100)	1.9	1.4	0.7	1.0	
<i>National trials</i>					
Faizabad, 1988 (37)	1.6	1.1	–	–	1.6
Pusa, 1988 (140)	3.8	0.6	–	–	(died)
Ghagharaghat 1988 (70)	1.6	1.9	–	–	1.1

^aMaximum water depths (cm) are in parentheses. ^bLocal check. ^cNational check.

NDGR150 and NDGR151 excelled in yield compared with national and local checks in preliminary trials at

Ghagharaghat UP (Table 1). Adaptive and national trials confirmed yield performance (Table 2).

NDGR150 is becoming popular in eastern UP because of its slender, white kernels and good cooking quality. □

Effect of incessant rain on seed health and measures to control damage

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Unprecedented rains (613.8 mm) in northern India during the last week of Sep 1988 caused widespread losses in the Punjab rice crop.

We collected 163 samples of PR106 from state districts to assess and upgrade seed health. We grouped seed into four categories according to crop lodging and flood intensity (Table 1). Three to five samples (4 m² each) per farmer's field were harvested.

L-I and L-II seeds were coated with white and dirty mycelial growth and had significant loss in seed vigor and yield; seeds in L-III and L-IV had 20–39% discoloration, light to chocolate brown spots, and black seeds.

Seeds in L-III and L-IV were subdivided into four categories based on discoloration severity (Table 1). Decreased germination was proportional to severity of seed discoloration. We studied field performance by laying out a 5- × 4-m plot in a randomized block design with five replications. Field performance of L-I and L-II categories was poor. Yield and yield parameters within discolored seeds did not significantly differ.

Seed microflora studies revealed that of 10 fungal species—*Fusarium moniliforme*, *Curvularia lunata*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Rhizopus* spp., *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Drechslera tetramera*, *Epicoccum purpurascens*, *Nigrospora oryzae*, and *Penicillium* spp.—the first four were most common.

F. moniliforme caused severe discoloration (light to chocolate brown) and white coatings on L-I, L-II, and L-III seeds. *C. lunata* formed a black crust or blotch-like coating on seed. About 57% of the L-I and L-II seed that had a higher

Table 1. Germination and field performance of rain-damaged and discolored PR106 seed.

Seed categories ^a	Seed vigor			Yield parameters				
	Germination (%)	Root + shoot length (cm)	Field emergence (%)	Tillers (no./plant)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)	Yield (t/ha)
L-I	13.6	6.2	5.0	10.0	81.3	21.7	120.0	3.0
L-II	25.8	9.7	15.6	11.8	82.7	23.3	132.3	3.4
L-III	69.0	15.4	64.5	15.4	116.7	28.5	170.2	4.9
L-IV	91.0	17.1	85.4	18.1	118.3	28.3	180.4	5.0
D-I	74.0	16.8	69.9	18.9	118.5	29.4	176.5	5.0
D-II	85.8	17.5	82.5	17.5	119.2	28.9	181.3	5.0
D-III	88.2	17.2	85.3	19.3	118.3	29.2	178.3	5.0
D-IV	96.0	17.7	94.2	18.6	119.2	28.1	179.2	5.0
LSD (0.05)	8.2	2.4	6.3	2.6	5.3	2.2	14.3	0.2

^a L-I = crop completely lodged and submerged, L-II = crop partially lodged and submerged, L-III = crop partially to completely lodged, but no stagnant water, L-IV = no lodging and stagnant water. D-I = fully discolored seed, D-II = more than half discolored seed, D-III = partially discolored seed, D-IV = healthy-looking seed.

Table 2. Effect of fungicides on germination of discolored seed.

Fungicide	Active ingredient	Dosage (%)	Germination (%)	Increase in germination over control (%)
Dithane M-45	Zinc ion (2%) and managous ethylene bisdithiocarbamate (75%)	0.3	84.6	10.4
Dithane Z-78	Zinc ethylene bisdithiocarbamate (75%)	0.3	83.7	9.7
Thiram	Tetramethyl thiuram disulfide (75%)	0.3	89.5	17.3
Captan	N-trichloromethyl thi-4-cyclohexane 1,2 dicarboximide (75%)	0.3	85.0	11.7
PCNB	Pentachloronitrobenzene (75%)	0.3	79.8	4.6
MEMC	2-methoxy ethyl mercury chloride (6%)	0.1	85.6	12.2
Streptocycline	Streptomycin sulfate (90%) and tetracycline hydrochloride (10%)	0.1	78.1	2.4
MEMC + Streptocycline	—	0.1+0.1	83.4	9.3
Derosal	Carbendazim-2-methoxy (carbonyl benzimidazole) (50%)	0.2	87.4	14.4
Carbendazim	Carbendazim-2-methoxy (carbonyl benzimidazole) (50%)	0.2	87.2	14.3
Thiram + Derosal	Carbendazim-2-methoxy (carbonyl benzimidazole) (50%)	0.2+0.2	93.3	22.3
Thiram + carbendazim	Carbendazim-2-methoxy (carbonyl benzimidazole) (50%)	0.2+0.2	93.2	22.2
Control	—	—	76.3	—

incidence of *A. flavus* were contaminated with aflatoxin (0.01–0.1 ppm). Yellow to dirty yellow bacterial slime that inhibited seedling growth and often caused death was associated with 19–49% of the categories.

None of the fungicides enhanced seed germination beyond 19.5% for L-I and beyond 37.3% for L-II. Tetrazolium test confirmed that seed viability was not more than 28.5 and 43.6%, respectively.

MEMC (mercurial fungicide) proved phytotoxic and lowered seed germination from 13.6 and to 2.8% for L-I and 25.8 to 14.5% for L-II.

Discolored seed germination was improved by applying a fungicide to control the seed microflora (Table 2). Thioram combined with Derosal and carbendazim provided the best control. All three were selective. □